

COGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF PROTOTYPICAL CHARACTERS IN ABDULRAZAK GURNAH'S BY THE SEA

Narbayeva Tursinay Muratbekovna

Uzbekistan State World Languages University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

narbaeva.tursynai@gmail.com

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Abstract

This article applies prototype theory within cognitive poetics to the analysis of characters in *By the Sea*. It examines how readers categorize Saleh Omar and Latif Mahmud as prototypical figures and how these categories are gradually complicated and reshaping the cognitive understanding of migration and belonging.

Key words: prototype theory, prototypical characters, cognitive poetics, categorization, refugee identity, migration, postcolonial narrative. reader cognition

Cognitive poetics allows us to study how readers understand characters and categorize them while reading.

[**Stockwell, Peter. Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction. Великобритания, Taylor & Francis, 2005. p.4**] One of the central ideas in cognitive poetics is the concept of prototype. Prototype theory was originally developed in cognitive linguistics by George Lakoff, who argued that categories are structured around central members rather than fixed definitions. [**Lakoff, George. Women, Fire, and Dangerous Things: What Categories Reveal about the Mind. United States, University of Chicago Press, 1987. p.6**]

According to Stockwell a prototype is the central, most typical example of a category around which other members are organized. It is not a fixed definition but a mental reference point that helps us recognize and classify people or concepts. For example, when asked to name a fruit, most people think of apples or oranges because they are central examples, while others like kiwi or mango are less typical. This shows that categories have fuzzy boundaries, with some members being more central than others [**Stockwell, Peter. Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction. Великобритания, Taylor & Francis, 2005. ch3 p.29**].

Gavins and Steen explain that categories work according to "family resemblance," meaning some members are closer to the prototype than others. A sparrow is considered a more typical bird than a penguin or ostrich. Importantly, prototypes depend on context and individual experience. They are flexible constructions formed in working memory rather than fixed mental structures. [**Gavins, Joanna. & Steen, Gerard. Cognitive Poetics in Practice. (2003). Великобритания: Taylor & Francis. ch.3 p.29**]

The novel *By the Sea* presents two main protagonists, Saleh Omar and Latif Mahmud. Their separate stories later connect and offer different views on migration, exile and belonging. In *By the Sea* Gurnah uses clear prototypical characters which help readers quickly recognize roles and social positions. Saleh Omar represents a typical refugee who shows nervousness, fear, worry and silence: *"..I am in the hands of time.... Now I live the half-life of a stranger.....guessing at the tireless alarms which afflict people I see in my strolls....but that their strangeness disarms me...I am trying too hard to make sense of the sight. It is not easy.."* [**Gurnah, Abdulrazak. "By the Sea" ch.1, p.2**]

His arrival at Gatwick Airport already activates the refugee prototype: *"I walked slowly through what felt like coldly lit and silent empty tunnels... I walked slowly so that I would not attract attention too early... No entry visa. Then he picked up his phone and spoke into it... Smiling openly now, he asked me to wait on one side."* [Gurnah, Abdulrazak. "By the Sea" ch.1, p5] He walks slowly, carefully observing signs and trying not to attract attention. His silence and anxiety correspond to what readers expect from a displaced and vulnerable migrant. These features allow readers to categorize him immediately.

Latif Mahmud represents another recognizable type. He is smart, educated, thoughtful and practical. Even though he teaches English literature, he says: *"I abhor poems. I read them and teach them and abhor them. I even write some. I teach them to students... and squeeze what I can out of them, make them short where they are long and showy, wise and clear where they are confusing"* [Gurnah, Abdulrazak. "By the Sea" ch.3, p.74]. This presents him as a responsible professional adult who performs his duties seriously despite personal dislike. He becomes a prototype of the educated intellectual migrant.

While Saleh Omar and Latif Mahmud function as central prototype based categorization in the novel, other characters also represent recognizable social types. For instance: Kevin Edelman is careful, proud and strict representing an authority figure. Hussein is clever and skillful in business functioning as a prototype of the experienced entrepreneur. Rachel is kind, caring and supportive representing the prototype of a social worker. All these prototypes allow readers to quickly recognize characters and predict their behavior.

However prototypes in the novel are not rigid. In different situations characters display unexpected features. For example Saleh Omar is not only a silent and anxious refugee. In the episode of the ebony table when Latif accuses him of not returning the table that belonged to his family Saleh admits: *"Greed. Meanness. It was a business. I wish I had given it back"* [Gurnah, Abdulrazak. "By the Sea" ch.5, p.158]. Here Saleh is not only a victim but also someone capable of moral failure. This complicates the refugee prototype and moves him away from a simple image of helplessness.

Similarly Latif's identity is not limited to the role of an intellectual. In the scene referring to The Odyssey when an elderly woman washes his foot and recognizes him echoing Eurycleia recognizing Odysseus [Gurnah, Abdulrazak. "By the Sea" ch.4, pp.127-128]. Latif becomes associated with the broader cultural prototype of the exile or the wanderer seeking home. This intertextual reference connects him to the cognitive model of the returning hero but in a postcolonial context where return is complicated and incomplete.

Stockwell notes that distant elements of prototypes include literary influences and genre traditions.

[Stockwell, Peter. *Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction. Великобритания, Taylor & Francis, 2005. ch3 p.26*] In *By the Sea* such distant elements include references to Herman Melville's "Bartleby, the Scrivener", "The Odyssey" and other classical works. These references enrich character prototypes by linking them to broader cultural and literary traditions. For example Saleh's silence recalls Bartleby's refusal, suggesting alienation in the face of bureaucracy. Through these distant associations, prototypes become layered and culturally embedded.

Postcolonial character prototypes in Gurnah's novel therefore have multiple levels. They include personal traits, social roles, historical background and intertextual references. Readers

who are aware of cultural and literary contexts can recognize these layers and deepen their understanding of the characters. [**Felicity Hand. *Becoming foreign:Tropes of migrant identity in three novels by Abdulrazak Gurnah/Felicity Hand - ResearchGate, 2012 - 4p***]

Prototypes also guide readers' expectations. When characters act according to their type, comprehension is smooth and immediate. When they deviate, attention increases. Saleh Omar's mixture of vulnerability and moral ambiguity destabilizes the simple refugee category. Latif Mahmud combines intellectual distance with emotional displacement. In this way Gurnah does not merely use prototypes but also he subtly reshapes them.

To sum up cognitive poetics helps explain how readers categorize characters in *By the Sea* and how these categories are gradually transformed. Prototypes allow quick recognition but the novel complicates them, showing that migration and belonging cannot be reduced to fixed social types. Through prototypical structures and their modification Gurnah presents characters who are at once recognizable and deeply complex.

References:

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